

ARDC Communities Strategy

THE APPROACH FOR THE ARDC IN RUNNING AND SUPPORTING COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE

ARDC Community Facilitators Group

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PURPOSE

The purpose of this strategy document is to emphasise the importance of managing ARDC Communities effectively and to outline an approach that ensures consistency and alignment with the ARDC's focus and strategy. This document replaces an earlier version created in September 2021, incorporating the current ARDC strategy to align the focus for ARDC managed Communities.

The ARDC is currently managing several communities that are aligned with the previous strategy. To ensure alignment with the updated strategy, it will undertake important work to review and assess these existing communities.

To help understand the changes needed in the management of Communities, it was necessary to evaluate the existing Communities of Practice (CoPs) and their alignment with the ARDC's new focus thematic Research Data Commons (RDCs), the Nectar Research Cloud, National Information Infrastructure (NII) and uplifting digital research skills. To support this, we gathered insights on the functioning of the existing CoPs, their target audiences and their capacity to support these strategic focus areas. The responses provided valuable information on the operation of existing CoPs and their alignment with the ARDC strategy, highlighting the potential contributions of these CoPs. This has helped with decision making around the continuation of the existing communities.

This strategy presents a 'Communities Review Process' which can be implemented to review current CoPs as needed.

INTRODUCTION

A simple definition of a 'Community' is as follows:

noun

1. a group of people living in the same place or having a particular characteristic in common
2. the condition of sharing or having certain attitudes and interests in common.

Both of these definitions are of relevance with regards to how the ARDC looks at communities and their management and support.

The ARDC works with and through communities in all their forms, including interest groups, working groups, communities of practice, user groups and program groups to develop and implement

best-practice Digital Research and data standards and approaches, and grow capacity in the Australian data and Digital Research sector. The communities formed will be pivotal mechanisms to support the strategic focus areas that are the core business for the ARDC. Communities bring together all the relevant stakeholders, resulting in community-agreed and supported standards and approaches. Taking a community wide approach also ensures capacity building takes place across the community, rather than in isolated pockets or restricted to specific projects. Having both agreed standards and approaches and a complete view of communities avoids the sector re-inventing the wheel and limits the duplication of effort. It will allow Australian researchers to efficiently use world leading approaches and tools, infrastructure and data and play a leading role on the international stage.

The ARDC forms Communities to enable the members to do something they are not able to achieve individually. Taking an active role in developing relevant communities will help transform sector capability, benefit all strategic focus areas, and prepare for sustainable communities to carry forward the capability building beyond ARDC involvement.

The aim of this strategy is to provide a consistent and effective approach across the ARDC when initiating, engaging with, and leaving communities. It enables the ARDC to monitor the impact of our involvement across a range of communities and will ensure that we make balanced decisions on which communities we support and will provide the basis for consistently high quality community engagement.

FOCUS

The ARDC's strategic focus spans thematic RDCs (in health and medical, earth and environmental, and humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research), the Nectar Research Cloud, NII and digital research skills. Within each strategy area it is anticipated that communities will be formed to facilitate conversations and collaborate on activities that address specific interests and key challenges in addition to the formation of new communities, strategy aligned focus areas will be able to tap into existing communities managed by the ARDC. Notably, existing communities such as i4iOZ, Vocabularies, Data Repositories, and ML4AU have relevance and maintain alignment.

Another key consideration for CoPs is their target audience as they influence the need for CoPs. Our primary audience is researchers, who we reach either directly or through our provider audiences, which includes universities and industry partners. We are keen to have involvement from many participants in the CoPs with the ultimate goal of benefiting Australian researchers.

The ARDC will focus on leading and supporting national communities that align with its core strategic objectives and activities, as well as NCRIS goals. This approach ensures projects, standards, and technologies can be articulated to a broader audience, increasing overall collaboration and transparency.

COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT

A community in which the ARDC might consider becoming involved in is defined by the following:

- The community is aligned with the core activities and strategy of the ARDC - one of the identified thematic RDCs, the Nectar Research Cloud, NII and/or digital research skills
- There is strategic value in the ARDC leading or convening this community
- There is no other organisation either already managing it or more appropriate to manage it
- There is evidence of sector need and interest in the topic area. For example, it aligns with the needs of People and/or, Planet and/or HASS&Indigenous
- It develops and discusses the implementation of best-practice standards and approaches relevant to research data, and Digital Research and the themes expressed by the ARDC strategy
- It grows sector capacity for research data and Digital Research skills
- It has national and potentially international coverage and meets national needs
- It is free and open for all relevant stakeholders to join
- It delivers useful outputs and solutions to the sector that are open and available to those outside the community.

LEVELS OF ARDC INVOLVEMENT IN COMMUNITIES

Clear alignment with ARDC goals and NCRIS principles is the minimum threshold for active involvement in a community. For each community it is important to define the extent of ARDC involvement. The possible levels of involvement are:

Leading

We lead (trigger the formation, setting of targets and agenda setting) and provide other support (e.g. operational, resourcing or in kind effort). We do this because we deem the group crucial in achieving the ARDC's strategic goals. Without ARDC this group would not exist or operate. Example group:

[Australian Vocabulary Special Interest Group \(AVSIG\)](#)

Co-leading

We lead with several other relevant organisations and may provide operational support. We do this because the challenges are best addressed by a joint group run by several key stakeholders in the National landscape, that extend beyond the ARDC. Example group: [*Sensitive Data Interest Group*](#).

Supporting

A different organisation leads and we may provide operational or other support (e.g. organising meetings, website, mailing list). We do this because without ARDC support this group would not exist or operate and we deem the group crucial in achieving the ARDC's strategic goals. Example group: [*Research Software Engineer Association of Australia and New Zealand*](#)

Participating

We participate as a member of the group representing the ARDC. We participate to be informed of the discussions taking place, to be aware of new technologies, standards and technologies that are relevant to the ARDC's strategic goals and to provide ARDC input into the work of the group. Example group: [*RDA Data Steward Career Tracks Working Group \(2025-2026\)*](#)

Monitoring

We do not participate in the group but do keep in touch to stay up to date and monitor for future strategic engagement. We monitor to stay broadly informed of the discussions taking place, to be aware of new technologies, standards and technologies that are relevant to ARDC's strategic goals. Example group: [*AusPreserves \(Digital Preservation Community of Practice\)*](#)

It is likely that we will undertake the role of 'co-leading' and 'supporting' for many of the new CoPs that are created for the thematic RDCs, Nectar Research Cloud, NII and Skills strategic areas as we will want subject matter experts to run them, we can support with maintenance and administrative tasks such as facilitation.

The [ARDC Communities and Groups webpage](#) provides current information on the Communities the ARDC leads, co-leads, supports, participates in and monitors.

TYPES OF ARDC LED, CO-LED AND SUPPORTED COMMUNITIES

Table 1. ARDC Communities

TYPE	PURPOSE	MEMBERSHIP	COMMUNITY MEMBER PARTICIPATION	TYPICAL DURATION
Interest group	<p>Keeping people in the loop</p> <p>Bring together persons with an interest in a specific area of interest or challenge. Enable them to share approaches and solutions to address these shared challenges.</p>	Open	Passive (attending and sharing)	Ongoing
Working group	<p>Specific short term activity</p> <p>Develop a specific documented standard, approach, or solution to a shared problem. In other words, a “task force”. May involve formal support e.g. contracts, resourcing.</p>	Defined (may be opt in, once established membership is generally fixed)	Active	Short term 6-24 months
Community of practice	<p>Transforming practitioner practice</p> <p>Bring together a defined group of practitioners to share expertise, knowledge and learn from each other, improving their practice, thereby growing the capacity in the sector.</p>	Open	Active	Ongoing
Program community	<p>Sharing and coordination amongst ARDC co-investment partnerships</p> <p>To ensure best practice is shared and partners are able to benefit from everything ARDC and other stakeholders have to offer.</p>	Restricted (to project partners in specific ARDC Programs)	Active	Fixed for the duration of the program
User community	<p>Collecting views and gaining agreement across the user community</p> <p>To keep our services are up to date and designed with the user in mind</p>	Open	Active	For the duration of the service

Other Communities

The ARDC participates in or monitors communities that are led by others, both nationally and internationally. We actively promote such communities as useful mechanisms to engage in the latest discussions and development of standards and solutions. An example of which is the ARDC’s involvement in working groups and interest groups as part of [The Research Data Alliance](#). ARDC staff act as co-chairs for many RDA groups and participants in that they attend meetings and are part of the regular RDA Plenary events. An example of such a group is the RDA Persistent Identifiers WG.

COMMUNITY LIFECYCLE

Applying a lifecycle approach helps to achieve clarity and manage expectations around community goals, required resourcing and plans for sustainability. It provides structure in founding and managing a community and provides a mechanism to wrap up or hand over communities. Typical activities for each phase are outlined below.

Emerging (typically about 6 months, but can be shorter)

- Exploratory activities collecting interest in a topic, for example issuing an Expression of Interest, or Request for Comment to communities
- Identifying areas of potential community involvement
- Canvas interest in the topic and scope
- Getting ARDC agreement to continue with the next steps to found this community
- Emerging community form is submitted to the Community Facilitators group for feedback
- Emerging community form is submitted to Manager of Engagements for approval (2 week process of review and approval)
- Manager of Engagements records approval status and communicates the result to the ARDC community lead.

Founding (typically about 2 months)

- Creating Terms of Reference with lead partners
- Initiating community place and norms

Active (typically 2 years)

- Pursuing shared goals
- Community and stakeholder management
- Leverage ARDC Outreach to share community outcomes. Ensure documentation is available for enduring national impact and outcomes are broadly communicated.

Review (To be conducted every 2 years for each community, this step takes 2 months)

- Community Lead: Evaluate goals and status of the community and whether they have been achieved, both by partners and members of the community
- Decide on whether the community should be continued, handed over or wrapped up.

To support the Review process the questions below guide the evaluation of ARDC involvement in communities, to determine whether to continue, hand over responsibilities or wrap up. These three steps cover internal evaluation, community evaluation and address leadership of the community.

1. Evaluate ARDC involvement

- Does it still meet the [principles](#) outlined above? That includes whether ARDC participation in this community furthers our strategic aims.

- What is the extent and impact of ARDC involvement in this community? How many resources does this require?
 - What are the overall expectations for the ARDC involvement in this community for the next 12 months?
2. Evaluate the usefulness of the community - SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats)
 - Survey partner and stakeholder demand and usefulness
 3. Leadership of the community and support for the community
 - If the ARDC support were to continue, does anything need to change?
 - Have community members (individuals or organisations) emerged as future leaders?
 - Is there effective and representative governance?

Following the review step, there are three possible outcomes:

Continue (keep community as Active)

- Pay attention to improvements as required, such as adjusting the Terms of Reference

Handover (typically 3 to 6 months)

- Review process has identified a suitable individual or organisation to replace ARDC involvement
- Community onboarding and offboarding procedures

Wrap up (typically about 3 months)

- Deal with group resources appropriately (e.g. publish these) so these can achieve enduring national impact
- Decommission group platforms (mailing list, Google Group page, slack workspace)
- Update status on public platforms (github repo, ARDC website)
- Communicate wrap up to community stakeholders.

PROCESSES FOR ARDC LED OR CO-LED COMMUNITIES

Emerging phase

1. One clear ARDC lead individual is (self) identified.
2. The lead will obtain support from their manager and sponsorship from an ARDC Director.
3. The lead will investigate community interest in the topic, noting that it has not yet been decided the community will be supported by ARDC.
4. The lead will complete an Emerging Community Profile and share and discuss at the Community Facilitators community of practice.

Approval phase

1. The completed Emerging Community Profile document will be passed onto the Manager of the Engagements team for review and approval
2. If required the proposed community will be discussed with the Director of Outreach to ensure compliance with the ARDCs goals and objectives, to ensure it aligns with the ARDC's strategy
3. Upon approval, the potential lead of the community will be notified

Founding phase

1. **Terms of reference** are drawn up that are supported by the community.
2. **Web presence:** Set up a public-facing mini-site to represent your group and share contact details. Follow ARDC guidelines and coordinate with the Communications team for support and inclusion on the main ARDC website. The ARDC Google site template for communities includes relevant ARDC policies (ARDC [Privacy Policy](#), [Code of Conduct](#)).
3. **Meetings and events:** Choose a consistent approach for managing events and tracking participation. Use internal procedures to support promotion and reporting.
4. **Share community outputs:** Community final outputs should be published via Zenodo, and shared via the community Google site.
5. **Communication and engagement plan:** Work with the ARDC Communications team to develop a communications and engagement plan that suits your audience and group goals. This will help you plan how you will encourage participation, promote group activity and share outputs with your broader target audience.

Active phase

1. **Launch:** Work with the Communication team to develop a plan to launch the community so that it reaches all your target audiences. For example, the Visible Research Software Interest Group was launched with [an article](#), which was shared in partner email newsletters, our newsletter and on social media. The group leader also sent emails to relevant people and email lists. Contact the Communications team to coordinate the launch promotion.
2. **Promote events and outputs:** The ARDC Communication team can help you grow your community by promoting meetings, events and outputs through our newsletter, website and social media, along with sharing these with external partners to promote. To promote your events or outputs, please email the ARDC Communications team.
3. **Record participation:** The value of the community is communicated through NCRIS reporting, senior level engagement and reporting to ARDC members. Record attendance of each meeting of the Community in an event campaign within Salesforce for reporting purposes. Please ensure researcher contacts are labelled as 'Researchers', as ARDC also reports on the number of researchers engaged with.

Review phase

1. Once every two years the community is reviewed to see whether there is still an ARDC need and community interest.

ARDC COMMUNITY FACILITATORS COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

Where ARDC supports a community we will try to ensure as many of these processes are followed where possible. Where a different organisation is leading there may be conflicting processes which may need to be met and agreed.

An internal Community Facilitators CoP is in place. Its scope includes:

- Supporting ARDC staff to lead communities effectively
- Evaluating current communities using the principles in this strategy
- Improving internal communication channels about respective community activities
- Harmonising the public face and participant experience of ARDC communities.

Meetings of this group are held monthly. Community facilitators meet and provide updates on their community's activities and other community related topics are discussed.

Promoting Communities

ARDC-led communities will need ongoing promotion to raise awareness of their existence, but also to show the value of the effort being invested in these. The ARDC will include the communities and their outcomes in NCRIS reporting and reporting to ARDC members through updates at internal cross-functional team meetings.

The existence of the portfolio of communities and their outcomes will be covered in our marketing, communications and engagements, for example in our newsletters, brochures and materials listing our products and services and senior and operational level engagement.

The communities will also be promoted individually to the relevant audience, for example when providing expertise into projects and when engaging with partners and in our newsletters. Interested parties will be made aware of relevant outputs and be encouraged to join the community that might be of interest to them.

The ARDC Communication Team can be contacted to coordinate the promotion of community, events and outputs.

SUMMARY

This document provides commentary on the direction and focus of Communities and illustrates the process for setting up new CoPs. Details are given towards options for the management of CoPs - the level of ARDC involvement that needs to be considered. The existing CoPs will continue to function and will be reviewed periodically to ensure they remain aligned with the ARDC's strategy and continue to contribute to the research landscape. New CoP requests will be reviewed by the Engagements Manager. It is envisaged that these new CoPs will be targeted to align with the ARDC's strategy.

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